

Measuring the H I gas mass of galaxies in the early universe with cosmic explosions

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Neutral atomic hydrogen (H I) is one of the most fundamental and dominant baryonic components of the first generation of galaxies. However, due to the weakness of the hyperfine 21-cm transition, the study of H I has been limited to the most nearby galaxies at $z \lesssim 0.3$ [1]. Even with next-generation radio facilities such as the Square Kilometre Array (SKA), this transition can only be detected from individual galaxies out to $z \approx 1.7$ [2]. This greatly motivates the use of a *proxy* to infer the H I content of the most distant galaxies. Here we present a new approach to link and calibrate the amount of H I to the bright fine-structure transition of singly-ionized carbon [C II]–158 μm in galaxies from $z \approx 1.5 - 6.5$, as presented in [3], using the optical afterglows of gamma-ray bursts (GRBs).

GRB afterglow sample

GRBs are known tracers of the dense, star-forming regions of high-redshift galaxies. Their short-lived optical afterglows further enables detailed studies of the interstellar medium (ISM) of their hosts (e.g. [4]). In this work, we analyse a set of carefully selected bursts detected by the Neil Gehrels Swift Observatory (*Swift*) over the last decade as part the X-shooter GRB (XS-GRB) afterglow legacy survey [5]. The sample criteria are constructed such that the observed sample provides an unbiased representation of the underlying population of *Swift*-detected bursts, while simultaneously optimizing the observability. We consider all GRB afterglows suitable to measure the column densities of the H I Lyman- α and the C II* $\lambda 1335.7$ transitions, which results in a sample of 15 bursts at $z \sim 1.5 - 6.3$ from which we can derive the relative abundance between H I and C II* in absorption. Figure 1 presents an example of the absorption-line modelling for one of the GRB afterglows in the sample. For each bursts, we can further measure the gas-phase metallicity, corrected by the amount of metals depleted onto dust grains.

The [C II]-to-H I conversion factor

The line transition C II* $\lambda 1335.7$ observed in GRB absorption spectra arises from the $^2P_{3/2}$ level in the ground state of ionized carbon (C⁺). The population in this state gives rise to the [C II]–158 μm transition ($^2P_{3/2} - ^2P_{1/2}$). From the column density of this particular feature, N_{CII^*} , we can thus determine the equivalent line luminosity based on the spontaneous decay rate as $L_{[\text{CII}]}$ = $h\nu_{\text{ul}}A_{\text{ul}}N_{\text{CII}^*}$ in the line of sight, where $\nu_{\text{ul}} = 1900.5 \text{ GHz}$ and $A_{\text{ul}} = 2.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for [C II]–158 μm . Similarly, we measure the line-of-sight H I column mass density $M_{\text{HI}} = m_{\text{HI}}N_{\text{HI}}$, with m_{HI} the mass of the H atom and N_{HI} the H I column density. From these two quantities, we derive

the relative [C II]-to-H I abundance ratio, $M_{\text{HI}}/L_{[\text{CII}]} = m_{\text{HI}}N_{\text{HI}}/h\nu_{\text{ul}}A_{\text{ul}}N_{\text{CII}^*}$, which we here denote $\beta_{[\text{CII}]}$. Assuming that the ratio of the derived column densities for each sightline is representative of the mean of the relative total population, $N_{\text{HI}}/L_{[\text{CII}]} = \Sigma_{\text{HI}}/\Sigma_{[\text{CII}]}$, the $\beta_{[\text{CII}]}$ calibration derived per unit column is equal to the global [C II]-to-H I conversion factor of the galaxy. This scaling is derived for each GRB in the sample and converted to solar units, M_{\odot}/L_{\odot} .

Figure 1: Illustration of GRBs as probes of the ISM in their hosts. Panel a shows the typical explosion sites of GRBs, and panels b and c show examples of absorption features from C II* $\lambda 1335.7$ and H I Lyman- α .

Figure 2 presents the $\beta_{[\text{CII}]}$ conversion factor derived for each GRB as a function of metallicity, including the best-fit scaling relation between the two. The $\beta_{[\text{CII}]}$ conversion factor is found to log-linearly scale with the metallicity, described by the following relation

$$\log(M_{\text{HI}}/L_{[\text{CII}]}) = (-0.87 \pm 0.09) \times \log(Z/Z_{\odot}) + 1.48 \pm 0.21 \quad (1)$$

where Z/Z_{\odot} is the relative solar abundance (with $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.69$ for $\log Z/Z_{\odot} = 0$), and M_{HI} and $L_{[\text{CII}]}$

Figure 2: GRB absorption-line measurements of the relative [C II]-to-H I abundance ratio as a function of metallicity. The black solid line and gray shaded region represent the best-fit linear relation and associated uncertainty. Observations and simulations of galaxies at $z \approx 0$ are shown for comparison.

are in units of M_\odot and L_\odot , respectively. For comparison, the sample of galaxies at $z \sim 0$ from the *Herschel* Dwarf Galaxy Survey, for which [C II] luminosities and H I gas masses from direct 21-cm observations have been inferred [6], are shown as well, in addition to the average values of a set of simulated galaxies at the same epoch [7]. These theoretical predictions and the local galaxy sample are observed to match well with the empirical relation of $\beta_{[\text{C II}]}$ observed for the GRB sample at $z > 2$, indicating a strong universal connection.

Results

To infer the H I gas mass of high-redshift galaxies, we compile a set of galaxy samples from the literature surveyed for [C II] emission, for which we can apply the $\beta_{[\text{C II}]}$ conversion factor. For the compiled set of [C II]-emitting galaxies at $z = 2 - 6$ presented in Figure 3, we infer H I gas masses in the range of $M_{\text{HI}} = 3 \times 10^9 - 2 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$. At red-shifts $z \gtrsim 1$, all galaxies are observed to have H I gas masses in excess of their stellar mass M_* , reaching an average of $M_{\text{HI}}/M_* \approx 3$ at $z \approx 5$, contrasting the low H I content of nearby galaxies. This is the first indication that H I dominates the total ISM mass and baryonic matter content of galaxies at $z \approx 5$.

With the $\beta_{[\text{C II}]}$ conversion factor, we further make predictions for the cosmic H I gas mass density in galaxies, ρ_{HI} , at $z \approx 5$. Adopting the relevant [C II] luminosity function

Figure 3: The H I gas mass excess, M_{HI}/M_* , of star-forming galaxies as a function of redshift. The galaxy samples surveyed for [C II] at $z \gtrsim 2$ are color-coded according to the specific reference they are adopted from. Colored boxes mark the 16th–84th confidence interval of M_{HI}/M_* for each sample.

at this redshift, we derive a [C II] luminosity density of $\mathcal{L}_{[\text{C II}]} = 2.8 \times 10^6 L_\odot \text{Mpc}^{-3}$. Assuming an average metallicity of $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.4$ (i.e., $\log(Z/Z_\odot) = -0.3$), we can convert this into ρ_{HI} using the $\beta_{[\text{C II}]}$ conversion factor, which yields $\rho_{\text{HI}} = 1.6^{+0.5}_{-0.4} \times 10^8 M_\odot \text{Mpc}^{-3}$ at $z \approx 5$. This estimate is in remarkable agreement with measurements of ρ_{HI} from damped Lyman- α absorbers (DLAs) at similar red-shifts (see [8] for a review).

We conclude that using [C II] as a proxy for H I, similar to how previous studies have relied on e.g. CO to infer the molecular content, is the current best alternative to probe the neutral atomic gas-phase in galaxies beyond the local Universe and out to the epoch of reionization.

References

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